

PEDAGOGICAL VALUE OF USING FUN ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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***Abstract.** In this paper the notion of fun activities in education is studied. The importance of fun activities in education such as songs, rhymes and games in teaching foreign language is analyzed. Teachers' views of pedagogical value of using song statement are surveyed.*

***Key words.** Fun activities, songs, rhymes, games, primary school, young learners*

Introduction

According to the critical period hypothesis, language acquisition should begin early. Children are more likely to become more proficient in a second language if they begin learning it sooner rather than later. According to the hypothesis, children between the ages of six and thirteen are the best candidates to learn a second language. Certain language acquisition skills decline after the critical period, according to researchers like Lenneberg and Bickerton [1].

Results and Discussion

Through fun activities children can learn a language better as learning becomes natural for them since these activities do not make them conscious that they are learning a language. In Uzbekistan, the education system is on the way of a proper learning atmosphere in children's English classes according to children's interest and psychological characteristics in the compulsory English education at the primary level. In order to develop of young learners' learning styles, songs, rhymes and games can be very effective tools for teaching children a foreign language.

Fun educational activities often involve hands-on experiences, problem-solving, and critical thinking. These activities promote active learning, where

students actively construct knowledge and understanding through their own exploration and interaction with the subject matter [2]. According to Chevikhbash, Yumuratachi and Mede [3], there are many strategies for teaching English as a foreign language to young learners. Many teachers prefer to use songs in teaching English. It was believed that teaching young learners English, as a foreign language, should focus on how to develop entertaining activities for enthusiastic minds of young learners in the 21st century classrooms.

The English coursebook for 2nd grade pupils in Uzbekistan is customized edition that includes original sources owned and licensed by the Cambridge University Press. The book is really good structured, almost in one of the two lesson there is one of the fun activities for the young learners. Here is the first lesson plan of the book [4]:

Vocabulary: *Ben, Olivia, David, Leo, Tina Numbers*

Grammar: *Hello. What's your name? How do you spell ...? What's this?*

Story value: *Play together*

Talk time: *Let's play!*

Animal sounds r, l The rabbit can run. The lion is lazy.

It is obvious from the plan of a lesson above, each lesson has one of the fun activities. There is a fun activity in story value part and talk time part. In the lesson there is alphabet song, listening and acting game.

We have also studied the benefits of songs and games in teaching English as other countries. The research used a descriptive methodology. The greatest techniques for gathering data that could characterize what actually exists are typically descriptive investigations. The participants of this study were selected, based on a convenient basis. Therefore, 2 primary school teachers were chosen to respond to the questionnaire items. The study was conducted in Tashkent in the academic year 2024-2025. With ages ranging from 23 to 40, the majority of participants were female (47 female and 18 male teachers). They have three to twenty years of experience teaching young pupils. The researchers in this study used a closed ended questionnaire to collect the data. The participants were asked

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to respond to the items by choosing one of options of a five-point Likert scale: (agree, strongly agree, disagree, strongly disagree, and undecided). There are other options, which include (always, often, sometimes, rarely and never); to identify how songs were chosen and what strategies were applied in the class. Following data collection, the researchers began the process of summarizing, evaluating, and debating the study's conclusions. The following conclusions were drawn from the questionnaire's data.

Teachers' Views of Pedagogical Value of Using Song Statement

Statement	Strongly Agree	Disagree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I believe that songs should be an essential part of the English language teaching curriculum for young learners.	28 43%	27 42%	9 14%	0	1 1,5%
I believe that songs present opportunities for young learners to show their skills in many language areas, such as, speaking.	15 23%	40 62%	9 14%	0	1 1,5%
I believe that songs are important in developing the listening skills of young learners.	19 29%	37 57%	6 9%	3 5%	0
I believe that songs are fun and full of pedagogical value.	22 34%	38 58%	3 5%	1 1,5	1 1,5%

As table 1 demonstrates, 85% of participants agreed that songs ought to be a fundamental component of the curriculum for teaching English to young students, whereas only 1.5% disagreed. Regarding point 2, responses showed that 85% of teachers thought that songs gave students a chance to develop various language skills, while 14% of them responded in a neutral manner. According to the results

of statement 3, 86% of the participants thought that songs were a useful technique for helping young students improve their listening abilities. Additionally, songs are entertaining and have a lot of educational value, according to 92% of them.

Conclusion. The majority of participants in questionnaire held favorable opinions regarding the educational value of song usage. Ways of getting children involved in learning English in order to get children involved in the language class and to ensure a natural anxiety-free language learning environment certain techniques could be applied. One of the best ways of getting children drawn in the language class is through fun activities. Among the fun activities songs, rhymes and games are the most effective ones to be used for children in the language class.

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